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OMEGA-3 FATTY ACID FOOD SUPPLEMENTS FOR CHILDREN

Ljilja Torović^{1,2,3}, Jelena Banović Fuentes¹, Mirjana Djermanović^{4,5}, Maja Hitl¹

¹University of Novi Sad Faculty of Medicine Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia
ljilja.torovic@mf.uns.ac.rs; 990d15@mf.uns.ac.rs; maja.bekut@mf.uns.ac.rs

²Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Center for Medical and Pharmaceutical Investigations and Quality Control, Novi Sad, Serbia

⁴University of Banja Luka Faculty of Medicine, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

mirjana.djermanovic@med.unibl.org

⁵Public Health Institute of the Republic of Srpska, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Introduction: Nowadays, parents are advised by pediatricians to introduce omega-3 fatty acid (FA) supplements in the diet of their infants and young children, in order to support normal vision, heart and brain health and immunity. Current dietary reference values specify adequate intake of omega-3 FA as 100 mg of docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) for infants from 7 month and 1 year old children as well as 250 mg of DHA and eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) for 2-17 years old children. This study aimed to assess intake of omega-3 FA from supplements intended for children.

Material and methods: Twelve omega-3 FA supplements intended for children (1 based on terrestrial plants, 3 on algae and 8 on fish oil) were collected from the markets of Republic of Serbia and Republic of Srpska and subjected to GC-FID analysis of FA composition, further used to calculation DHA and EPA intake.

Results: EPA and DHA were abundantly present in fish and algae supplements, while absent from black currant and soy oil, characterized with presence of essential alpha-linolenic (ALA). Recommended dosage of supplements could provide: 125-217% (fish) of the DHA amount recommended for infants; 214-217% (algae) and 120-361% (fish) of the DHA for 1 year old; 87-88% (algae) and 74-255% (fish) of EPA+DHA for 2-3 year old; 41.6% (algae) and 132-644% (fish) of EPA+DHA for older children, with the exception of one supplement containing only ALA.

Conclusion: Considering the importance of EPA and DHA in children nutrition, their scarcity in common diet and limited ability of human body to convert ALA to EPA and DHA, fish and algae oils need to be acknowledged as more favorable supplemental sources of omega-3 FA.

Keywords: children, fatty acid, food supplement

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